

Review

Elections and Democratic Consolidation: A Study of 2019 General Elections in Nigeria

Ojukwu, U. G.*, Mazi Mbah, C. C. and Maduekwe, V.C.

Department of Political Science, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author E-mail: ojukwuuche04@gmail.com

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The main thrust of this paper is to examine elections and democratic consolidation in Nigeria with reference to the 2019 General elections. Elections are central to the existence, stability and development of democracies; and political parties play significant role in such democracies. The viability and preference of democracy as a form of government above others is predicated on the unique prominence, relevance and opportunity it affords for popular participation. It is against this backdrop that this work examines the successes and challenges recorded in the 2019 General elections in Nigeria with a view to providing a better alternative for an improved election in the future. This study adopted the Elite theory by Gaetano Mosca, Vilfredo Pareto and Robert Michels as its framework of analysis. The data used for this study were collected through the secondary sources which were obtained from the review of related literature. Despite the appreciation that only credible election can consolidate and sustain Nigeria's nascent democracy, election often result to confrontations that continue to threaten the political stability, peace and the very existence of the nation. The

major findings of the research are: that the 2019 general elections were to a large extent fraudulent as they did not largely reflect voters' choice due to inflation of election result figures, multiple voting, falsification of election results, delay in commencement of voting, result manipulation and wholesale subversion of the will of people which were largely perpetrated by the incumbents. The study also found out that the 2019 general elections have lower democratic quality and higher credibility deficit as compared to 2015 general elections. Most voters were induced with money by politicians both those in power and those seeking to be in power to influence voter's choice of candidate or political party in order to retain or capture political power. The research recommends that the areas that recorded significant improvement should be maintained while in the areas where there were of challenges should be looked into against future elections.

Keywords: Elections, electoral process, democracy, democratic consolidation, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Elections in post-colonial Nigeria and after independence have been vexed issues. This is because they have always been accompanied with acrimony, bitterness, killing, maiming, among others. The last elections held in Nigeria under British colonial rule were in December 1959. The elections ushered in Nigeria's independence on October 1st, 1960, while the first post colonial general election took place in December 1964. As campaign for the election started, the United Progressive Grand Alliance (UPGA), one of the coalition parties that fought the elections, alleged intimidation and denial of freedom

to operate by the Nigerian National Alliance (NNA), the opposing coalition, against its candidates. The situation degenerated that UPGA resolved to boycott the elections. There was tension in Nigeria, as a way out of the crisis, broad-based government was agreed upon. However, in less than one year, that is in November 1965 another election crisis engulfed Nigeria. This has to do with elections into the Western Nigeria House of Assembly. The ruling party in that region, the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) made sure that many candidates of the opposition parties were unable to get

their nomination through and ballot papers were made available to its supporters well in advance.

In addition, regulations that dealt with the counting of votes and the announcing of results were not adhered to. Eventually, the NNPP was declared winner of the elections. Consequently, the announcement unleashed a reign of violence on the region. "Operation we tie" that is, sprays fuel and set lives and property ablaze. As the violence continued, the Nigeria army on January 15, 1966 stepped in to stop further bloodshed and destruction. As part of efforts to disengage the junta from political scene and return to the barracks, the army organized elections in 1979. There were allegations of election rigging and other malpractices were also observed. As a result, the Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN), one of the parties that took part in the elections, went to court to challenge the result. We are aware of this term "stolen Presidency", which has since become part of Nigeria's political vocabulary. In the 1983 general elections, the ruling party, the National Party of Nigeria (NPN), was returned to power. The UPN complained bitterly over rigging of the election as was done in 1979. On the 31st of December, 1983, the junta (boys in khaki) intervened once more and took over the government. It is also true to say that the presidential election of June 12, 1993 was also dogged by controversy. It was organized as the last phase of the timetable to end the junta's rule. The election believed to be the freest and fairest in Nigeria's post-independence history, was cancelled by the Army itself because a body, the Association for Better Nigeria (ABN) that alleged corruption in the nomination of Chief M.K.O. Abiola, had gone to court and obtained a ruling that the election be postponed and the electoral umpire, the National Electoral Commission (NEC) failed to abide by the ruling.

The 1999 general election to finally disengage the military from politics were also rigged like previous elections in Nigeria. There were allegations on shortage of electoral materials at the Polling centres, thumb printing of ballot papers outside polling centres, about voting returns bearing little resemblance to the poor turnout of voters, etc. The All Peoples Party (APP)/Action for Democracy (AD) alliance went to court to challenge the declaration of the Peoples Democracy Party (PDP) candidate Olusegun Obasanjo as the winner. In the 2003, 2007 and 2011 elections, in such level of malpractices were even alleged to have taken place. It was alleged that ballot boxes were said to have been snatched from electoral officers and substituted with already stuffed ones by political thugs. Double thumb printing and voiding of votes cast for the opponent was alleged to have been carried out. In some centres, according to reports, electoral officials failed to turn up, and consequently there was no voting at such centres. In spite of this, results were later allegedly declared for them. In some others, results were allegedly "doctored and monitored" through collaboration between

officials of the electoral body and party agents. It was further reported that a lot of eligible voters were disenfranchised (Osaghae, 1999, pp. 4–25).

Nigeria struggles for sustainable democracy, good governance, and development have been so daunting that all previous attempts at democratic transition have been futile. The collapse of the First Republic (1960–66) and Second Republic (1979–83), and the abortion of the Third Republic through the annulment of June 12 1993 presidential election, are clear indicators of the failure of previous attempts at democratization. After a prolonged military rule characterized by the wanton violation and repression of the political, economic, and social rights of the people, the re-democratization process began in 1999 elicited renewed expectations for the consolidation of democracy in the country (Osaghae, 1999). At the heart of these expectations lie the pertinent issues of elections. Elections are meaningfully democratic if they are free, fair, participatory, competitive, and legitimate. This is possible when they are administered by a neutral authority; when the electoral administration is sufficiently competent and resourceful to take specific precautions against fraud; when the police, military and courts treat competing candidates and parties impartially; when contenders all have access to the public media; when electoral districts and rules do not grossly handicap the opposition; when the secret of the ballot is protected; when virtually all adults can vote; when procedures for organizing and counting the votes are widely known; and when there are transparent and impartial procedures for resolving election complaints and disputes (Diamond, 2008).

The aftermath of vote rigging by desperate political office contenders manifest in bad governance and extension of poverty. Often times, social and economic infrastructure development are neglected, there are threats on security of lives and properties. The pseudo-capitalist hegemony continues to raise its hydra head to sustain the masses economic deprivation and bleak political future. After fifty years of developmental retardation orchestrated by political servitude, Nigerians through April 2011 elections resolved to rescue the dying giant from its comatose state. They voted for a change, a change from unimpressive past and status-quo; to a new order that was expected to initiate a new dawn in the history of Nigeria and national development. The people who have for so long been eluded with good governance and its associated benefits; stood to the rescue of the nation that suffers from the plaque of its leaders. In unity of action, the people turned out massively and voted for candidates of their choice amidst political harassment and intimidation. They decided to salvage Nigeria's deeming political relevance among the committee of nations. They sacked all the non performing political parasites and elected new leaders whom they authorized to exercise political power on their behalf for the next four years.

Elections in Nigeria continue to elicit more than casual interest by Nigerian scholars due to the fact that despite the appreciation that only credible election can consolidate and sustain the country's nascent democracy. Over the years, Nigeria continues to witness with growing disappointments and apprehension inability to conduct peaceful, free and fair, open elections whose results are widely accepted and respected across the country (Igbuzor, 2010; Osumah and Aghemelo, 2010, Ekweremadu, 2011). All the elections that have ever been conducted in Nigeria since independence have generated increasingly bitter controversies and grievances on a national scale because of the twin problems of mass violence and fraud that have become central elements of the history of elections and of the electoral process in the country (Gberie, 2011).

Despite the marked improvement in the conduct of the 2011 elections, the process was not free from malpractices and violence (Bekoe, 2011; Gberie, 2011; National Democratic Institute, 2012). Thus over the years, electoral processes in the history of Nigeria's democratic governance have continued to be marred by extra ordinary displays of rigging, thuggery, "do or die" affair, ballot snatching at gun points, violence and acrimony, boycotts, threats and criminal manipulations of voters' list, brazen falsification of election results, the use of security agencies against political opponents and the intimidation of voters (Omotola, 2010; Bekoe, 2011). In fact elections remain one of the leading notable sources of conflict which often result to confrontations that continue to threaten the political stability and peace of the nation (Gueye and Hounkpe, 2010; Idowu, 2010).

Arguably, democratic culture or development is not sustainable on the conduct of good elections alone, other democratic virtues must be put in place and its efficiency must be ensured. Check and balances between the three arms of government, independent and incorruptible judiciary; viable fourth estate among others, are democracy sustaining tenets that should not be compromised. In a situation where the trust of the people is deflated by those entrusted to defend its sanctity, the masses should be irrepensible in their collective action to deal decisively with such betrayer of public confidence. Government whose actions and policies are inimical, and runs contrary to the expectations and total development of Nigerians should be voted out. Civil disobedience, walk to rule, peaceful and coordinated mass protest by a legitimate trade union or organized labour are few examples of how an anti-people's government could be legally run down in order to sustain our fragile democracy and hold the political leaders accountable. This paper is therefore, a bold effort to examine how elections in Nigeria have impacted on democratic consolidation in the country.

ELECTIONS IN NIGERIA

The evolution of electoral process in Nigeria has been arduous and protracted. Since Nigeria's independence in 1960, the country has organized nine general elections and numerous regional/State/Local elections. Of these elections, the 1979, 1993, and the 1999 polls were conducted by military regimes to allow for transition to civil rule, while the other elections were conducted by incumbent civilian regimes to consolidate democratic rule. Elections organized by incumbent civilian regimes have been the most problematic (Agbaje and Adejumo, 2006). With the exception of the 2011 and 2015 elections, these elections have been characterized by attempts by the ruling parties to contrive and monopolize the electoral space and deliberately steer the process in their favour. This pattern was reflected in the simulated landslide victories recorded by the ruling parties in the 1964, 1983, 2003 and 2007 elections (Ibeanu, 2007).

The 1964 Federal election was contested by the United Progressive Grand Alliance (UPGA), which was a coalition of predominately Southern parties, and the Nigerian National Alliance (NNA), whose base of support was in northern Nigeria. The Northern People's Congress (NPC) and its allies in the NNA took advantage of their control of the federal government to contrive victory (Dudley, 1973). The 1983 general elections were also manipulated by the incumbent National Party of Nigeria (NPN), which won presidency and gubernatorial elections in seven out of the nineteen States, and thereafter attempted to extend its political power throughout the federation. The allegations of vote manipulation in 1983 elections triggered violent protests in some parts of Nigeria (Hart, 1993).

The 2003 and 2007 general elections were also allegedly manipulated (Lewis, 2003; Suberu, 2007). The 2007 election in particular, severely dented Nigeria's democratic credentials due to the national and international condemnation they elicited. However, on a rather positive note, the election led to a great deal of soul-searching among the Nigerian leadership. The President at the time, Umaru Musa Yar'adua, publicly acknowledged that the election that brought him to office was fundamentally flawed. He therefore set up the Electoral Reform Committee (ERC) to suggest measures that could improve the conduct of elections; restore electoral integrity and strengthen democracy in Nigeria. Some of the Electoral Reform Committee's recommendations were reviewed and adopted as amendments to the constitution and Electoral Act. The government also tried to restore the integrity of elections in the country by appointing credible leadership to the INEC. For its part, the INEC adopted series of internal measures aimed at restoring public confidence in the electoral process (Kuris, 2012).

The recently concluded 2019 elections only succeeded in repeating the fraud and manipulations witnessed in the 1998, 2003, 2007 and 2011 earlier elections under PDP administration to a farce level.

Political succession remains contentious and highly challenging in many African countries. The privileges associated with power and the fear of being prosecuted by their successors causes some leaders to maintain control of the political process even through electoral manipulation and violence. For some years, the design of electoral systems to encourage cooperation, bargaining and interdependence between rival political leaders and the groups they represent has become increasingly crucial for the promotion of democracy in poor and divided societies. This seems to have made it increasingly difficult to hold elections without violence or protest in such settings. As political elites see elections as a means to capture the state apparatus and the resources it commands, electoral processes have come under severe threat. When will Nigeria and for that matter Africa as a whole conducts elections that would be transparent, credible and generally acceptable to all. Nigeria does not seem to be making progress at establishing a credible democratic electoral practice. This is sad given the size and economic clout that country commands in Africa. It is from the above background that this paper intends to look at efforts at democratization as well as assessing the efforts or process in the Nigerian experiment with the view of suggesting the way forward for sustainable democracy not only in Nigeria but also to States of similar political experiences.

General elections were particularly characterized by violence, rigging and official manipulation in favour of the parties in power. The factors that undermine the conduct of free and fair elections in Nigeria are multifaceted and occur at various stages of the electoral process. The election-day malpractices and post-election manipulation of the electoral process, repeated during the 2003, 2007, 2011 and 2019 elections, even with the introduction of card readers, were no less significant than the experience of the past. This time around, the manipulation reached such a feverish stage that it became commonplace and was done with impunity and fun fare. More damaging reports were produced in respect of the 2019 elections. The 23rd February and 9th March, 2019 elections in Nigeria and their reportedly unpleasant outcomes thus seem to present an opportunity for us to take a good look at the elections to find out why free and fair elections have been unattainable for years.

SOME HIGHLIGHTS OF NIGERIA'S 2019 GENERAL ELECTIONS

This sixth general election in this Fourth Republic is the first to be conducted by the Professor Mahmood Yakubu-led Independent National Electoral Commission. Although since coming into office in November 2015, his team has conducted 196 off-season governorship and other by-elections, the announcement of the date for this

year's elections was made two years ago, precisely on March 9, 2017. The elections were the most planned for. Preparations started with the INEC Strategic Plan 2017 – 2021; thereafter, there were Election Management System, Election Project Plan and Elections Operations Support Centre. A factsheet on the 2019 General Election revealed that there were 84 million registered voters out of which 72 million voters collected their Permanent Voter Cards; 91 registered political parties; 119,973 Polling Units; 120 Accredited Domestic Observers and 36 Accredited Foreign Observers and 23,000 candidates competing for 1,558 positions. Seven elections were also conducted over two Saturdays. They were Presidential, Senate and House of Representatives elections on February 23 and Governorship, State Houses of Assembly, chairmanship and councillorship elections of the six Area Councils of the Federal Capital Territory held on March 9, 2019. This was unprecedented in Nigeria's electoral history.

General elections were held in Nigeria on 23 February 2019 to elect the President, Vice President, House of Representatives and the Senate. The elections had initially been scheduled for 16 February, but the Election Commission postponed the vote by a week at 03:00 on the original polling day, citing logistical challenges in getting electoral materials to polling stations on time. In some places, the vote was delayed until 24 February due to electoral violence. Polling in some areas was subsequently delayed until 9 March, when voting was carried out alongside Gubernatorial and State Assembly elections.

Besides, the elections are the costliest in Nigeria's history. Officially, the Federal Government funded the elections with a whopping N242bn, N189bn of which went to INEC while the remaining N53bn was shared by the security agencies for the purpose of election security. This is outside the millions of dollars spent on the commission by the various international donor partners. The President of Nigeria is elected using a modified two round system, to be elected in the first round; a candidate must receive a majority of the vote and over 25% of the vote in at least 24 of the 36 states. If no candidate passes this threshold, a second round is held. The results of the presidential election were announced in the early hours of 27 February 2019 (Table 1). Incumbent President Muhammadu Buhari won his reelection bid, defeating his closest rival Atiku Abubakar by over 3 million votes. According to Ojo (2019) "He has been issued a Certificate of Return, and will be sworn in on 12th June 2019" (Punch Newspaper, Wednesday March 20, 2019).

Being the most competed for; this year's elections have also attracted a lot of controversies. From October 7, 2018, when political parties finished conducting their primaries, there have been over 640 court cases from aggrieved aspirants (Punch Newspaper, Wednesday March 20, 2019). The electoral commission is joined as defendants in all these pre-election cases. In the lead-up

Table 1. 2019 Presidential Election Results.

Candidate	Party	No. of Votes	%
1. Buhari Muhammadu	All Progressives Congress	15,191,847	55.60
2. Abubakar Atiku	People's Democratic Party	11,262,978	41.22
3. Felix Nicolas	Peoples Coalition Party	110,196	0.40
4. Mailafia Obadiah	African Democratic Congress	97,874	0.36
5. Gbor John Wilson Terwase	All Progressives Grand Alliance	66,851	0.24
6. Yabagi Sani Yusuf	Action Democratic Party	54,930	0.20
7. Akhimien Davidson Isibor	Grassroots Development Party of Nigeria	41,852	0.15
8. Ibrahim Aliyu Hassan	African People's Alliance	36,866	0.13
9. Donald Duke	Social Democratic Party	34,746	0.13
10. Omoyele Sowore	African Action Congress	33,953	0.12
11. Da-Silva Thomas Ayo	Save Nigeria Congress	28,680	0.10
12. Shitu Mohammed Kabir	Advanced Peoples Democratic Alliance	26,558	0.10
13. Yusuf Mamman Dantalle	Allied Peoples' Movement	26,039	0.10
14. Moghalu Kingsley Bosah Chiedu	Young Progressive Party	21,886	0.08
15. Ameh Peter Ojonugwa	Progressive People's Alliance	21,822	0.08
16. Ositelu Isaac Babatunde	Accord Party	19,219	0.07
17. Durotoye Adetokunbo Olufela	Alliance for New Nigeria	16,779	0.06
18. Bashayi Isa Dansarki	Masses Movement of Nigeria	14,540	0.05
19. Osakwe Felix Johnson	Democratic People's Party	14,483	0.05
20. Abdulrashid Hassan Baba	Action Alliance	14,380	0.05
21. Nwokeafor Ikechukwu Ndubuisi	Advanced Congress of Democrats	11,325	0.04
22. Maina Maimuna Kyari	Northern People's Congress	10,081	0.04
23. Victor Okhai	Providence People's Congress	8,979	0.03
24. Chike Ukaegbu	Advanced Allied Party	8,902	0.03
25. Ezekwesili Obiageli Katryn	Allied Congress Party of Nigeria	7,223	0.03
26. Ibrahim Usman Alhaji	National Rescue Movement	6,229	0.02
27. Ike Keke	New Nigeria People's Party	6,111	0.02
28. Moses Ayibiowu	National Unity Party	5,323	0.02
29. Awosola Williams Olusola	Democratic People's Congress	5,242	0.02
30. Muhammed Usman Zaki	Labour Party	5,074	0.02
31. Eke Samuel Chukwuma	Green Party of Nigeria	4,924	0.02
32. Nwachukwu Chuks Nwabuikwu	All Grassroots Alliance	4,689	0.02
33. Major Hamza Al Mustafa	Peoples Party of Nigeria	4,622	0.02
34. Okotie Christopher Oghenebrorie	All Blended Party	4,554	0.02
35. Shipi Moses Godia	Fresh Democratic Party	4,523	0.02
36. Fasua Tope Kolade	Abundant Nigeria Renewal Party	4,340	0.02
37. Rev. (Dr.) Onwubuya	Freedom And Justice Party	4,174	0.02
38. Dr Asukwo Mendie Archibong	Nigeria For Democracy	4,096	0.01
39. Ahmed Buhari	Sustainable National Party	3,941	0.01
40. Salisu Yunusa Tanko	National Conscience Party	3,799	0.01
41. Shittu Moshood Asiwaju	Alliance National Party	3,586	0.01
42. Obinna Uchechukwu Ikeagwuonu	All People's Party	3,585	0.01
43. Balogun Isiaka Ishola	United Democratic Party	3,170	0.01
44. Obaje Yusufu Ameh	Advanced Nigeria Democratic Party	3,104	0.01
45. Chief Umenwa Godwin	All Grand Alliance Party	3,071	0.01
46. Israel Nonyerem Davidson Dr.	Reform and Advancement Party	2,972	0.01
47. Ukonga Frank	Democratic Alternative	2,769	0.01
48. Santuraki Hamisu	Mega Party of Nigeria	2,752	0.01
49. Adesanya-Davies Mercy Olufunmilayo	Mass Action Joint Alliance	2,651	0.01
50. Gbenga Olawepo-Hashim	Peoples Trust	2,613	0.01
51. Ali Soyode M.	Yes Electorates Solidarity	2,394	0.01
52. Ojinika Geff Chizee	Restoration Party of Nigeria	2,391	0.01
53. Nsehe Nseobong	Coalition for Change	2,388	0.01
54. Rabia Yasai Hassan Cengiz	National Action Council	2,279	0.01
55. Atuejide Eunice Uche Julian	National Interest Party	2,248	0.01
56. Dara John	Alliance of Social Democrats	2,146	0.01
57. Fagbenro-Byron Samuel Adesina	Kowa Party	1,911	0.01
58. Etim Emmanuel Ishie	Change Nigeria Party	1,874	0.01
59. Chukwu-Eguzolugo Sunday Chikendu	Justice Must Prevail Party	1,853	0.01
60. Madu Nnamdi Edozie	Independent Democrats	1,845	0.01
61. Osuala Chukwudi John Kennedy	Re-build Nigeria Party	1,792	0.01

Table 1. Contd.

62. Albert Owuru Ambrose	Hope Democratic Party	1,663	0.01
63. David Esosa Ize-Iyamu	Better Nigeria Progressive Party	1,649	0.01
64. Inwa Ahmed Sakil	Unity Party of Nigeria	1,631	0.01
65. Akpua Robinson	National Democratic Liberty Party	1,588	0.01
66. Mark Emmanuel Audu	United Patriots	1,561	0.01
67. Com. Ishaka Paul Ofemile	Nigeria Elements Progressive Party	1,524	0.01
68. Kriz David	Liberation Movement	1,438	0.01
69. Ademola Babatunde Abidemi	Nigeria Community Movement Party	1,378	0.01
70. A. Edosomwan Johnson	National Democratic Liberty Party	1,192	0.00
71. Abah Lewis Elaigwu	Alliance for a United Nigeria	1,111	0.00
72. Angela Johnson	Change Advocacy Party	1,092	0.00
73. Nwangwu Uchenna Peter	We The People Nigeria	732	0.00
Invalid/blank votes		1,289,607	-
Total		28,614,190	100
Registered voters/turnout		82,344,107	34.75

Source: INEC 2019. (Computation into percentage was made by the Researchers).

to the elections, there was a constitution amendment that now pegged the time limit for pre-election matters to fourteen days. Hitherto, there used to be no such thing but on June 8, 2018, President Muhammadu Buhari signed into law the Fourth Alteration No. 21 which now asks all aggrieved aspirants to file their matter within 14 days of the action while courts are to deliver judgments on such matters within 180 days while appeals from such judgments shall also be disposed off within 60 days.

Immediately following the elections, there were claims of widespread fraud by the opposition. The claims included accusations of ballot box snatching, vote-trading and impersonation. There were also claims that caches of explosives were found by police. While the African Union said the elections were "largely peaceful and conducive for the conducting of credible elections". The electoral commission also described the elections as mostly peaceful. However, the 2019 election fell short of expectations. Informed commentators rightly identified the process smashing records. Standards dropped! We had to deal with having too many political parties on our ballot. The electoral manager INEC presented 91 parties to us. Some 73 presidential aspirants, an unprecedented figure in the history of our democracy, expressed interest in leading the country to greater heights. Some of them withdrew, thus could not complete the race. Validation of the elections now rests with the court (THISDAY, Monday, April 8, 2019). It was during the 2019 elections that a court of law denied a ruling party at the centre the opportunity to contest all elections in Rivers and Zamfara states. Due to the lingering dispute over the party congresses held in Rivers State in May 2018, the High Court, Court of Appeal and even the Supreme Court barred the APC from fielding candidates for all elective positions in the state. Two states, Zamfara and Rivers, were initially involved before the Zamfara High Court came to the rescue of the Zamfara APC by ordering INEC to enlist the party on the ballot paper.

Another thing that singled out the 2019 general election was the high number of cancelled votes due to violence, over-voting and non-adherence to the use of Smart Card Readers. The cancelled votes which are in millions brought about, five inconclusive governorship elections in Kano, Sokoto, Plateau, Adamawa and Benue State. INEC initially enlisted Bauchi among the states before reversing itself after a review of the investigative panel it set up on the governorship election. There were also seven inconclusive governorship elections, 24 inconclusive House of Representatives election and three inconclusive Area Council chairmanship polls in the FCT. Supplementary elections in the Polling Units where elections were cancelled in the affected states were to hold on Saturday, March 23, 2019.

Something unprecedented in the annals of Nigeria's electoral democracy was INEC's review of the decisions of its Returning Officers in Imo West Senatorial Election and Bauchi State governorship election. In Imo State, the Returning Officer for the Imo West senatorial election, Prof Innocent Ibeawuchi, alleged that he was forced to declare Okorochoa the winner of the poll by the supporters of the APC candidate. He was reportedly held hostage from 7pm on Sunday, February 24 till 11am on Monday, February 25. The don said because he feared for his life, he had to announce the result which he claimed was inconclusive, because of the alleged electoral fraud in eight LGAs. For allegedly making its Returning Officer to declare result under duress, INEC has withheld the Certificate of Return for Okorochoa. The question is, where were the security agents meant to protect INEC officials?

In Bauchi State, INEC similarly reviewed the declaration of his Returning Officer concerning the nullification of the result of Tafawa Balewa Local Government Area. According to the commission, its investigative panel found out that halfway into the LG collation, armed gangs attacked the collation centre and

destroyed the LG Result Sheet (EC8C) and some collated results from the Registration Areas. The results of seven out of the 11 Registration Areas for governorship and six out of the 11 for state Assembly elections were affected. The collation officer, under pressure from party agents who could not wait for the arrival of a replacement result sheet, decided to collate the result on an available RA result sheet instead of the replacement LGA result sheet. "The investigation committee also established that the number of cancelled votes for the four Polling Units in Ningi LGA which was recorded as 25,330 in Form EC40G (1) was incorrect. The actual figure is 2,533.

The big question which has attracted litigation is whether INEC as a commission can overrule its appointed Returning Officer in the light of provision of Section 68 of the Electoral Act 2010, as amended which states that: "The decision of the Returning Officer on any question arising from or relating to: (a) Unmarked ballot paper, (b) Rejected ballot paper, and (c) Declaration of scores of candidates and the return of a candidate shall be final subject to review by a tribunal or court in an election petition proceedings under this Act." This was why the governor of Bauchi State, Alhaji M A Abubakar, has dragged the commission to court urging it to halt the resumption of collation of results of the Tafawa Balewa LG. Of the 29 states where gubernatorial and state houses of assembly elections held on March 9, six of them – Adamawa, Bauchi, Benue, Kano, Plateau and Sokoto – had to go through supplementary elections. Now, we know that rerun are trajectories for intimidation, suppression, inducement and violence. Ballots were burnt in Benue. Thugs attacked journalists and disenfranchised voters in Kano. Voters were induced in Bauchi (Table 1).

The 109 members of the Senate were elected from 109 single-seat constituencies (three in each state and one for the Federal Capital Territory) by first-past-the-post voting. The 360 members of the House of Representatives were also elected by first-past-the-post voting in single-member constituencies. Currently, 64 incumbent Senators will not be returning as members of the Ninth Senate, having been defeated during the elections. While the APC will have a simple majority of votes in the Senate, it will not have a supermajority (74 votes), meaning it cannot push through major bills on its own (Table 2).

The Governorship general election was conducted in 29 states with APC winning 15 States while PDP won 14 States. Election did not take place in 7 states in 2019. The above results indicated that State Governorship election took place in 29 of the 36 states in the country as the calendar for election in other states differed (Table 3). The ruling party APC won 15 out of 29 making a total of 51.7 % of the states while the opposition PDP won 14 or 48.27% of the seats. The governorship election did not hold in seven states of the federation and the Federal

Table 2a. Result of 2019 National Assembly Elections (Senate and House of Representatives).

Party	Seats (Senate)	Percentage
All Progressives Congress	64	58.7
People's Democratic Party	44	40.4
Young Progressive Party	1	0.9
Total	109	100

Source: "Election Centre". <https://nigeriaelections.stearsng.com>. Retrieved 06-04-2019; Omotayo, (2019).

Table 2b. House of Representatives.

Party	Seats (House of Reps.)	%
All Progressives Congress	216	60
People's Democratic Party	124	34.4
All Progressives Grand Alliance	10	2.7
African Democratic Congress	3	0.8
People's Redemption Party	2	0.6
Action Alliance	2	0.6
Social Democratic Party	1	0.3
Young Progressive Party	1	0.3
Labour Party	1	0.3
Total	360	100

Source: "Election Centre". <https://nigeriaelections.stearsng.com>. Retrieved 06-04-2019; <http://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3101>.

Capital Territory (FCT). The affected states, Anambra, Bayelsa, Edo, Ekiti, Kogi, Ondo and Osun, did not participate because their governorship elections were held at different times. This was mainly due to court judgments that nullified the elections of their governors at different times in the past. However, the State Houses of Assembly elections were conducted in all the 36 states. The FCT did not witness both elections because it is run by a minister, who is appointed by the President, with laws made by the National Assembly but Councillorship elections took place. After dealing with arson and postponement, more challenges lurked around for INEC. Apathy came to devour our electoral process. Apathy ejected its host, INEC and ate to its fill. This affected votes recorded at the polls on February 23 and March 9, 2019. It appeared citizens had lost confidence in the process initially scheduled for February 16 and March 2. Their minds were made up (THISDAY, Monday, April 8, 2019). Questionable figures influenced victories against the wishes of the people. Results were declared at gun points. But again, voters had themselves to blame for not showing up at polling units on Election Day. Although they can't feign ignorance of conspiracy at collation centres, apathy fuels and prepares the ground for the enthronement of compromise.

Cash determined the winners and losers. 'Secure the bag' rose in ranks at the expense of contesting to serve the people. Bullion vans moved freely on our streets. We saw no wrong in this yet we answer the title – propagators of

modern democracy. We helped Nigerians to strip and banish democracy and its principles in the scheme of things. Transactional politics wrestled with ideologies. One may suggest it did not just start now but it has come to stay. Cash couples with brawn and impunity threw ideological politics out of the ring. Cash chose leaders for us. And we saw nothing wrong with that. Those that got some naira notes should realize they have no moral right on fellows who offered them money to secure electoral victory (THISDAY, Monday, April 8, 2019).

Our elections are now fiercer and “more competitive”. We have shut our eyes and ears to making elective positions unattractive. Our elections have become what we can refer to as “anything goes and business minded” (THISDAY, Monday, April 8, 2019). We now know that politicians don't come to serve us. They come to swindle; to siphon and to serve themselves. They come all out to water the path of their children and their children's children.

CHALLENGES OF 2019 GENERAL ELECTIONS IN NIGERIA

Nigeria's democracy landed on a good platform with the existence of democratic institutions, plural society, vibrant civil society organizations and critical mass media among others. These ingredients have the structure and capacity to make democracy thrive in Nigeria. But it is germane to note that, Democracy in Nigeria has remained grossly unstable since the return to this popular form of governance in 1999. The political terrain has been home with lots of challenges precipitating against the genuine realization of the system. In fact, the impediments to the nations unending desire for a true democracy seem to assume a more perilous proportion by the day. Some of the major challenges faced in preparation and conduct of the 2019 general elections relate to the cynicism and skepticism of the Nigerian voters and citizens generally; the peculiar attitudes and mindset of the typical Nigerian politician; those associated with the use of technology in our infrastructure-challenged environment; the constraints imposed by the extant legal framework and those emanating from the prevalence of the phenomenon of weak institutions and other systematic peculiarities of the Nigerian polity.

Ethno-religious factor

This remains one of the forces that have contributed greatly to socio-political instability in the country. The latest sectarian turbulence in the country and the clamour for the presidency by the varied ethnic groups indicate that the society is still balkanize by tribal and religious sentiments (Victor, 2002).

Each ethnic nationality in Nigeria has its own faith, interest, culture, language and level of aspiration and these forces seems to affect the economic fate of each group. In addition, they make the creation of a common identity problematic, thereby exacerbating the difficulty in attaining a true democracy in the society. Currently, Nigeria lacks the necessary democratic values (civil and human abuse is rampant, freedom of speech and expression are hampered, lack of social security and distributive justice) hence the rampant social unrest in the polity (Victor, op.cit). For one, the manipulation of ethno-regional identity reached new heights in the march towards the elections, making the election to appear like a form of warfare between the North and the South. In the build up to the election, there were campaigns by local PDP activists urging voters in the South East not to support the APC, describing the party as a reincarnation of the Northern-Yoruba alliance that defeated Biafra in the Civil War of 1967-1970. Following the APC victory, there was a growing perception that the APC government would alienate the South-East and South-South, in the same way the two regions were marginalized in the aftermath of the civil war. For another, the seemingly unprecedented level of elite fragmentation, also along ethno-regional and religious lines was another source of serious concern.

Technology adaptation in an infrastructure-challenged environment

The Electoral Management body recognized, quite early, the need to increasingly use technology to improve the conduct of elections in Nigeria. One key challenge is, associated with the virtual absence of Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs). Virtually everything has to be sourced through vendors, and imported from abroad, who impose extortionate conditions, arbitrarily review upwards licensing fees on account of ‘proprietor’ rights. As most technology relies on electricity, inadequacy of power supply requires additional expenses on batteries, spare parts and redundancies. INEC tried to appropriate technology, albeit through vendors, but with effort to curtail their total control, by signing on to contracts with detailed specifications and use of Open Source Software. But doing this also has its own challenges. There are also other associated challenges. For example, meeting the production deadlines in the production of PVCs was seriously affected by power failures, which damaged equipment, which the vendor could not quickly replace. The use of the Smart Card Reader (SCR) was constrained by the fact some polling units are located in areas where there was no internet coverage or in schools, which used as RACs, with no electricity to charge batteries and Smart Card Readers. The smart card readers and the welfare of ad-hoc staff continue to constitute challenges to the electoral process. INEC is yet to match commitments with action on prompt payment

and adequate welfare for ad-hoc staff. The malfunctioning and deliberate non-usage of the smart card reader continues to hinder the smooth running of the elections.

Apathetic and skeptical citizenry

The average Nigerian has been so profoundly frustrated, disappointed and devastated by the crude manifestations of the mechanics of Nigerian electoral politics, so much so that they have become either apathetic and indifferent, or exceedingly cynical or skeptical. According to Ojukwu *et al.* (2016) the significance of this is that political apathy is not natural; it is influenced and can be motivated by many factors. Once bitten, it is said, twice shy. Nigerian citizens and voters have been 'bitten' several times in politics and in elections. The civic duty of going out to vote in elections had become very dangerous, exposing voters to risks of being assaulted or injured or killed by armed thugs doing the bidding of some politicians, or by some deranged militants and terrorists. If they succeeded in casting their votes unscathed, they watch helplessly as the votes were stolen, or the election results purchased from cooked election and security officials, such that for all practical purposes, their votes don't count. In the circumstances, many citizens have withdrawn from the electoral process and/or have become extremely skeptical about the value and utility of elections. While elections were to help institutionalize good, democratic governance, what they see are elected people running amok as reckless despotic rulers, vandalizing and looting public resources and ignoring the core business of government of social provisioning to satisfy the needs and aspirations of the people, and providing protection for lives and property of citizens. Given this context, it was a herculean task for INEC and its partners to convince citizens that this time around it would not be "business as usual".

Disjointed information

Mass media as watchdog of the public interest is very crucial to democratic consolidation. The media is democratically seen as vanguard for holding governments accountable and guarding against the abuse of power. This can be done by raising countervailing structures of surveillance to monitor government activities and stem an inherent disposition towards excesses. But in Nigeria especially in this republic, there are constraints on press media resulting in suppression of information, provision of disjointed and half hazard information and thereby limiting the capacity of individuals to develop a reservoir of political knowledge to assist them in controlling authoritarian rule and participating adequately in political activities.

Our media has been subsumed into the elite structure "the big man" syndrome or "upper body structure". This is actively inimical to the survival and deepening of democracy (Awuudu, 2012).

The incumbency factor

In political parlance, incumbency refers to holders of political office who enjoy certain privileges (such as wider media coverage and security) which are not available to other contestants in the electoral contest. These privileges create some electoral margin for the incumbent running for re-election leading to an incumbency abuse factor. In Nigeria, this factor promotes appointment of corrupt and or compromised electoral officers, manipulation of the electoral law and the constitution, manipulation of the electoral tribunals to protest stolen mandates, use of state security forces and apparatus to intimidate opposition parties, denial of access to state owned media houses etc to ensure they regain or elongate their tenure against popular will (Nwanegbo and Alumona, 2011).

The Politics of God-Fatherism

Another great impediment to democratic consolidation in Nigeria is the phenomenon of god-Fatherism which has been dominating the political scene of the country. It is a game where political kingmakers and gladiators manipulate the political system to enthrone their crowned political stewards. Ogundiya, (2010) asserts that God-Fatherism is both a symptom and a cause of the violence and corruption that together permeates the political process in Nigeria. Public officials who owe their positions to the efforts of a political godfather incur a debt that they are expected to repay without end throughout their tenure in office. They control state resources and policies not minding the corporate existence of the state. In fact their activities help frustrate the basic democratic values in society and block the democratic process by obstructing selection of good and qualified candidates for elective posts thereby making the rise of true democracy a hard nut.

Corruption

According to John Campbell, USA Ambassador to Nigeria; corruption is a clog in the wheel of any nation struggling for the enthronement and consolidation of democracy and good governance (Punch July 7th, 2005). This shows that democracy cannot be predicted on a fragile and unstable political base. Corruption as a devastator has greatly eroded the fundamental values of democracy and its essential principles.

Corruption in its popular conception is defined as the exploitation of public position, resources and power for private/selfish gain. For instance, Dobel, (1978) defined corruption as “the betrayal of public trust for individual or group gain”. In a similar vein, Obayelu, (2007) identifies it as “efforts to secure wealth or power through illegal means for private gain at public expense, or a misuse of public power for private benefits”. According to Ogundiya (2010), events in Nigeria since 1999 have shown that the tidal waves of reversal have been contending with Nigeria’s democratic project. Consequently, democracy remains grossly unstable and the future seems to be very bleak because of rampant bureaucratic and political corruption. Corruption has reached a high crescendo such that an average Nigerian now possibly associates democracy with it. The consequences of political corruption are potently manifest: cyclical crisis of legitimacy, fragile party structure, institutional decay, chronic economic problem and unemployment, and above all general democratic volatility.

Corruption in this country is generally characterized by looting of funds and wealth kept secretly, i.e. capital flight; misappropriation and mismanagement of public funds; money laundering (acquiring money through fraudulent ways); drug and child trafficking; illegal arms deal; gratification which involves monetary, material or physical favour as a condition or reward for performing official duty, official abuse of office in which an official suppresses and violates an oath of office and nepotism which is granting undeserved favors to one’s relations. The recent corruption scandal in the oil sector totaling N1.7 trillion from 1999-2011, Police Pension Fund of ₦18 billion as well as the James Ibori N450 billion corrupt case of money laundering in London is just the tip of an iceberg as far as corruption is concern in Nigeria.

Constraints of extant legal framework

A good legal framework is a necessary precondition for credible elections. It is international best practice to review an existing legal framework to make it better for the conduct of elections, provided that this is done within the internationally mutually agreed timeframe, i.e. at least six months before a general election. In the Nigerian context, the 2010 Electoral Act (as amended) was no doubt a remarkable improvement over the 2006 Electoral Act. It is along with constitutional provisions on electoral matters was the legal framework for the conduct of the 2011 general elections. Nevertheless, it had many areas requiring improvement and we strove to that long before 2019. For example, the constitution requires a runoff election, if or when it becomes necessary, to be held within 7 days after the elections. We were lucky that in 2010 we did not have to do a runoff election even for the governorship elections, because it would have been very difficult to pull it through. A presidential runoff election is

almost certainly impossible within 7 days. So INEC recommended an amendment to that provision to at least 3 weeks, although the international best practice seems to be around 6 weeks. INEC also wanted an amendment to provision in the Electoral Act 2010 (as amended), Section 31, which contradicted another, Section 87, and which undermined internal party democracy. There are many other areas where amendments would have been consequential and would have added value to the electoral legal framework.

Multiple electoral challenges, credible periodic election are a crucial factor in the survival of any political system and the conduct of free and fair election is the beauty of a democratic structure. This is because it makes electoral activities meaningful and the interest of the electorates represented. But in Nigeria especially in this fourth republic, elections have become a tool for promoting the interest of the aristocrat rather than the electorates. The philosophical basis and fundamental ethos of democracy are being swept under the carpet making the Nigerian electorates to lose faith in the electoral process and governance. Analytically, the 2003, 2007 and 2019 general elections were adjudged to be worst elections in the history of fourth republic. This is because the elections were characterized by; massive rigging, monetization factor, assassination, political thuggery, sentiments, corrupt practices of electoral officers, judicial injustice, deliberate disfranchisement of the populace, discountenancing of the electorate’s vote, outright disregard for the rule of law, political inquirer, etc. What the above implies is that the legitimacy of democracy as the best form of governance has been corroded.

FACTORS NECESSITATING ELECTORAL REFORMS

Inokoba and Kumokor, (2011) in examining the electoral history of Nigeria posit there is a general consensus that the integrity of elections has been on the decline since 1959 with the 2007 general elections widely assessed by both local and international observers as the worst in the country’s history before the poorly organized 2019 elections. The electoral reform is of immense importance in Nigeria especially if Nigeria wants to enjoy dividends of democracy and achieve tremendously in her quest for development. Thomas Pickering (1998) opined that, enduring stability can come to Nigeria only from a representative government that is accountable to its citizens, respect their rights, and guided by the rule of law. There has been struggle over the years to find amicable ways to engender confidence in the conduct of free and fair elections in Nigeria. This struggle can be said to be two sided; first is how to design and ensure an efficient, effective and politically nonpartisan election management body, and second is on how to re-orient the country’s political culture so that the political elite and general public will show a genuine commitment to the

rules and regulations governing the electoral process in Nigeria hence ensure credible and acceptable election. The issue of credible election has occupied the minds of Nigerians, Africa and the International community due to the strategic position of Nigeria in Africa. On the part of Nigerians, they have appreciated the tenets of democracy and believe that it is only through democracy that they can directly participate in the affairs of their country.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

When elections are credibly conducted, they imbue the government with legitimacy garnered by the consent of the people, improving the capacity of the state to ensure community security through legitimate authority under the rule of law. It also improves the level of human development through effective governance. Credible elections create legitimate governments that enjoy popular support for programmes and policies. This study indicates that Nigeria has some challenges in electoral process particularly in sustaining democracy. The 2019 general elections have been particularly disastrous because they were characterized by falsification of election results, stuffing of ballot boxes, announcing results in places where no elections were held, inflation of figures, illegal possession and thumb-printing of ballot papers, delay in commencement of voting, compilation of fictitious names on voter's lists, results manipulation and wholesale subversion of the will of people all of which were perpetrated largely by political office holders which posed challenge to the conduct of free, fair and credible elections. The result of our investigation also reveals that crises of elections in 2019 were partly due to partiality, incompetence and partisanship of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) as it compromised the electoral processes.

The study also found that the 2019 general elections have credibility deficit as they generated petitions and litigations. The study also discovered that the processes of conducting 2019 general elections were characterized by harassment and oppression of persons by the political office holders to those belonging to the opposition parties or considered to be critical of their mismanagement of electoral process with the use of law enforcement agencies. There was massive deployment of police and armed forces which frightened and threatened voters. This widespread militarization of the society by those in power during elections undermined the credibility of the elections. In essence, the incumbents control and manipulate the electoral system to their advantage which eroded the credibility of 2019 general elections.

An equally important finding from the outcome of this study is that, the electoral malaise have implications for democratic consolidation in Nigeria as democratic stability cannot be super-imposed or predicated on a

shaking, unstable and unpredictable crises-ridden social and political environment as the chances that Nigeria's democracy with flourish are undoubtedly becoming slimmer and slimmer after each elections due to post-election violence in protests of irregularities which may not only affect the legitimacy of government but also the citizen's affection or believe in democracy as a suitable model of government (Abdullahi, 2014).

However, the research also concludes that there were many challenges faced by the election and it was not that totally successful as many scholars, local and international observers and commentators speculated or concluded in their analysis. There are many serious challenges that hindered the smooth operation or total success of the election and these challenges are legal, procedural and logistical which must be looked into and address by the electoral body, policy makers, civil societies, international supporting agencies, parties, contestants, electorates and all stakeholders that are involved in the electoral process in Nigeria in the future. As a result, the research recommends the following:

(a) Government at all levels should deal with issues of mass poverty and unemployment. As long as people remain poor and lack access to basic means of livelihood, they will remain susceptible to all kinds of manipulations by politicians, including being used to ferment violence during and after elections which pose challenges to credible, free and fair elections in the country.

(b) The calibre of INEC's leadership is crucial. A mechanism for choosing people with both competence and integrity is essential if INEC is to develop as a functional institution that can improve its capacity to deliver free and fair elections.

(c) Politicians in Nigeria should imbibe genuine democratic culture and learn to relegate their personal interests to supreme national interest which is peace, political stability and economic development by allowing popular expression to decide who should be in control of political leadership during conduct of elections. For democracy to thrive and for Nigeria to continue to enjoy international legitimacy, their value orientation must change. Election must no longer be seen as the end of everything.

(d) On electoral offences, a very powerful incentive for continuous breaches of the law and for electoral fraud seems to be that those who violate the Act are never punished. It is recommended that in any petition once a criminal allegation is proved beyond reasonable doubt, the offender should be sentenced to part of the consequential decision of the court. What is more, the law is that once there is a criminal imputation it must be proved beyond reasonable doubt. This will send a strong signal to all that it cannot be business as usual.

(e) The need to encourage the culture of opposition politics is of crucial importance to the future of Nigerian

democracy. It is widely known most Nigerian politicians always prefer to be on the winning side and would therefore prefer to strike deals with the winning party. It is defeatist attitude. It would serve the course of democracy better if opposition parties remain steadfast; build strength and capacity around their programmes and manifestoes to provide the electorates with credible alternatives in future elections.

(f) There should be a comprehensive electoral reform in which all stakeholders including civil society organizations and international funders and observers should ensure that the quality and credibility of elections in Nigeria are not compromised in order to ensure the epitomic expression of popular choices (Abdullahi, 2014).

(g) We implore INEC to find a lasting solution to address the perennial card reader challenges and poor handling of the welfare of ad-hoc staff. It is also vital that there is a uniform application of rules on the non-usage of the card reader.

Authors' Declaration

We declare that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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